

The Influence of Work Ability, Servant Leadership, and Workload on Employee Performance through Organizational Commitment at Secretariat East Java Province Marine and Fisheries Service

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ABSTRACT: The objective of this study is to examine the impact of work ability, servant leadership, and workload on employee performance, with organizational commitment serving as a mediating factor, at the East Java Province Maritime and Fisheries Service. This research offers both theoretical and practical advantages. This study employs a quantitative methodology. The data were gathered by a questionnaire that was issued to workers of the Secretariat, Maritime and Fisheries Service of East Java Province via an online form. This study used a saturation sampling strategy, which involves including all members of the population as respondents or selecting a sample of 71 individuals. The SEM-PLS statistical technique was utilized to conduct testing on the 7 stated hypotheses. The research findings indicate the following relationships: 1) Work ability has a significant impact on employee performance; 2) Work ability has a significant impact on organizational commitment; 3) Servant Leadership has a significant impact on employee performance; 4) Servant Leadership has a significant impact on organizational commitment; 5) Workload has a significant impact on employee performance; 6) Workload does not have a significant impact on organizational commitment; 7) Organizational commitment has a significant impact on employee performance.

KEYWORDS: Work Ability, Servant Leadership, Workload, Employee Performance, Organizational Commitment

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the government's attempts to implement significant reforms and modifications to the government administration system, particularly with regard to institutional (organizational) features, management, and personnel resources of the apparatus, is bureaucratic reform. An efficient and productive system of government administration is being established through bureaucratic reform. The foundation of changes in national and state life is bureaucratic reform.

One of the implementations of bureaucratic reform that is the target of work at the Maritime and Fisheries Service of East Java Province is the realization of employees of the Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Service who are competent, professional and have integrity. This is related to the performance of the Maritime and Fisheries Service of the Province of East Java employees who are the object of this research.

Orderly management of personnel affairs is an implementation of quality Bureaucratic Reform, so matters related to personnel management must be carried out well. However, in practice there are several obstacles caused by various possible factors such as work ability, servant leadership, workload, and organizational commitment among employees, resulting in employee performance not being met with predetermined targets.

The 25 items of personnel data include: Name/NIP, half body photo, full body photo, KTP, KK, Karpeg, Taspen, NPWP, CPNS SK, PNS SK, Rank SK, Education SK, 2022 SKP, 2023 SKP, periodic salary, type of position, structural position, functional position, executive position, Retirement Age Limit (BUP), marriage, type of employment, legal position of employee, origin of employment, and PPPK Decree.

An employee's organizational commitment reflects their understanding of the company and their devotion to its objectives (Kreitner & Kinicki, 2011). Meanwhile, according to Rashid et al. (2003) in Mujanah et al. (2019) A psychological state known as organizational commitment illustrates the bond between workers and their organization. It can be seen from the OPD achievement data that it also shows a lack of organizational commitment because there are still many who have not updated the East Java DKP Virtual ASN Card in the last ten months. Movement seems slow even though the virtual ASN card is an obligation for every employee and is used for individual personnel administration. The updated data is taken into account as organizational performance which is reported every month by the Regional Civil Service Agency of East Java Province.

According to Mathis & Jackson (2006) one of the performance indicators can be assessed through employee attendance. In an organization, this means coming to work, leaving work, permission or without information, all of which affect the employee's

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performance. Hasibuan (2001: 34) states that A person's performance is the outcome of the duties they are assigned, which are determined by their skill, experience, seriousness, and time constraints. Quantity, quality, timeliness of work results, attendance, and the capacity to collaborate are all components of employee performance that are common to the majority of employees.

The research carried out by Mailisa et al. (2016) states that there is no substantial impact of organizational commitment on employee performance. Recent studies conducted by Purwanto et al. (2022), Nafiudin et al. (2023), and Marsilia et al. (2024) have shown that organizational commitment significantly influences employee performance.

The East Java Province Maritime and Fisheries Service is burdened by a substantial caseload, necessitating the assistance of qualified human resources. A caseload is a collection or quantity of activities that an organizational unit or position holder is required to complete within a specified time frame, as per Dhania (2010: 16). In accordance with Hersey and Blanchard in Agus Dharma (1995: 5-6) Having the ability to operate efficiently and effectively in one's chosen profession is a quality that is present in workers. There has to be an increase in human resource capability in relation to this job capacity.

In order to realize good governance, leadership is needed that can synergize with its subordinates and there is good interaction in managing the burden and large potential in the Maritime and Fisheries Service of East Java Province. Trompenaars & Voerman (2010: 3) define servant leadership as a management style that is in harmony with the environment and involves both directing and serving. A servant leader is someone who can effectively integrate the inclination to serve and lead in a constructive and mutually beneficial way.

Research conducted by Rachman et al. (2021), Dani & Mujanah (2021), and Ludwikowska (2023) has demonstrated a significant correlation between servant leadership and employee performance. In contrast to the research conducted by Mujanah & Arivani (2022), which claims that servant leadership does not have an influential impact on employee performance.

The research carried out by Pakpahan et al. (2021) Servant leadership does not have a substantial impact on organizational commitment. In contrast to three other studies done by Dani & Mujanah (2021), Fariana et al. (2022), and Tanuwijaya et al. (2023), which provide evidence that servant leadership significantly influences organizational commitment.

Since there is a lack of research proof, the researchers will apply it to the Maritime and Fisheries Service of East Java Province.

II. THEORETICAL STUDY

A. Organizational Behaviour Theory

According to Wardiah (2016: 181), organizational behavior is the study of individual behavior within organizational groups, which is directly related to other fields of study. The main component or key supporter of an organization's functioning is humans. However, an organization is greatly influenced by the behavior of each individual within it. These differing human behaviors will affect the behavior within the organization.

According to Robbins & Judge (2013), researching organizational behavior is a discipline that focuses on the influence of individuals, groups, and structure on organizational behavior. It aims to apply knowledge to enhance organizational effectiveness. As a field of study, organizational behavior examines three determinants within an organization: individuals, groups, and structure. Organizational behavior applies knowledge about behavior in relation to work activities and the performance outcomes of organizational members.

B. Work Ability

Work aptitude is a person's capability to do different activities within a certain employment (Robbins and Judge, 2009: 57). According to Thoha (2011), One of the components of maturity is ability, which is connected to information or skills that one may acquire by means of education, training, and experience. Work ability is a multifarious quality reflecting the interplay between the volume of physical and mental tasks, workers' functional capacities, their health, and their subjective evaluation of their position within certain organizational and social settings (Kaela, 2006: 170).

The indicators of the work ability variable in this study refer to Raharjo, et al. (2016), which are:

1. Knowledge
2. Training
3. Experience
4. Skills
5. Work capability

C. Servant Leadership

According to Trompenaars and Voerman (2010), Servant Leadership is a management style where leading and serving are in harmony and involve interaction with the environment.

According to Dennis (2004), Servant Leadership can be measured using the Servant Leadership Assessment Instrument (SLAI). Based on this, the indicators of servant leadership are as follows:

1. Compassion

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2. Empowerment
3. Vision
4. Humility
5. Trust

D. Workload

According to Tarwaka (2015:106), workload can be defined as a discrepancy between a worker's capacity or ability and the demands of the job that must be met.

The workload indicators according to Tarwaka (2015) are:

1. Time Load
2. Mental Load
3. Psychological Load

E. Organizational Commitment

According to Mujanah et al., in Dani & Mujanah (2021), organizational commitment is a psychological condition that reflects the relationship between employees and their organization. Organizational commitment is an important work attitude because employees with organizational commitment are expected to demonstrate a willingness to work harder to achieve organizational goals and possess a strong desire to serve in a company.

Robbins (2008: 101) categorizes organizational commitment into three separate indicators:

1. Affective Commitment
2. Continuance Commitment
3. Normative Commitment

F. Performance

According to Ambar Teguh Sulistiyani (2003: 223), an individual's performance is a combination of ability, effort, and opportunity that can be assessed based on their work results. Maluyu S.P. Hasibuan (2001: 34) stated that performance (work achievement) is the result of work achieved by an individual in carrying out the tasks assigned to them, based on their skills, experience, dedication, and time.

The performance indicators according to Mathis & Jackson (2012) are:

1. Quality
2. Quantity
3. Timeliness
4. Attendance
5. Ability to work in a team

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Based on the conceptual framework described above, the research hypotheses are as follows:

H1: Work Ability has a significant effect on Employee Performance.

H2: Work Ability has a significant effect on Organizational Commitment.

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H3: Servant Leadership has a significant effect on Employee Performance.

H4: Servant Leadership has a significant effect on Organizational Commitment.

H5: Workload has a significant effect on Employee Performance.

H6: Workload has a significant effect on Organizational Commitment.

H7: Organizational Commitment has a significant effect on Employee Performance.

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

A. Data Type and Sources

This investigation is quantitative in nature causal exploratory research analysis which will explain the causal relationship between exogenous variables (work ability, servant leadership, and workload) on endogenous variables (employee performance) and intervening variables (organizational commitment). This research uses a questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale measurement for primary data collection. Next, data analysis employs SEM-PLS statistical techniques.

B. Population and Sample

Population in this study consists of employees working in the Secretariat Unit of the East Java Province Department of Marine Affairs and Fisheries, totaling 71 individuals. This study employs a saturated sampling technique, where all members of the population are taken as respondents or samples. Thus, the sample size in this study amounts to 71 individuals.

C. Data Collection

The data collection technique used in this research is an online questionnaire distributed via Google Forms. This study employs two sections in the questionnaire:

1. The first section contains statements aimed at obtaining general information about the respondents to determine the alignment of their characteristics with the criteria, such as employee type, gender, highest education level, age, and length of service.
2. The second section contains statements aimed at collecting data related to the research variables, namely work ability, servant leadership, workload, organizational commitment, and employee performance, to measure the data according to the indicators.

D. Data Analysis Method

The analysis method used for analyzing the questionnaire data is the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method to test hypotheses about the relationships between latent variables (not directly observable) and manifest variables (directly observable).

Descriptive analysis in this study is conducted to describe respondents' responses for each research variable. Quantitative data analysis uses the SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) model. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is a statistical technique used to solve hierarchical models simultaneously, which cannot be resolved by linear regression equations. Data processing and analysis in this study utilize Smart PLS SEM (Partial Least Squares – Structural Equation Modeling).

Hypothesis testing is determined based on the t-statistic value and probability value. For hypothesis testing using the statistical value, with an alpha of 5%, the t-statistic value used is 1.96. Thus, the criteria for accepting or rejecting a hypothesis are as follows: H_a is accepted, and H_0 is rejected when $t\text{-statistic} > 1.96$. For hypothesis testing using probability, H_a is accepted if $p\text{-value} < 0.05$

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Description of Research Variables

Table 1. Variable Class Interval

Interval Kelas (Class Interval)	Work Ability	Servant Leadership	Workload	Organizational Commitment	Performance
$1,00 < IK \leq 1,80$	Sangat Rendah	Sangat buruk	Sangat ringan	Sangat Rendah	Sangat Rendah
$1,81 < IK \leq 2,60$	Rendah	Buruk	Ringan	Rendah	Rendah
$2,61 < IK \leq 3,40$	Lumayan tinggi	Lumayan baik	Sedang	Lumayan tinggi	Lumayan tinggi
$3,41 < IK \leq 4,20$	Tinggi	Baik	Berat	Tinggi	Tinggi
$4,21 < IK \leq 5,00$	Sangat tinggi	Sangat baik	Sangat berat	Sangat tinggi	Sangat tinggi

Source: SEM-PLS Output

The NT value of five originates from the highest scale on the questionnaire reply, even if the NR of 1 derives from the lowest scale on the questionnaire. IK is the number of response classifications adjusted to the number of Likert scales. Drawing on the average computation of every indication on the questionnaire, the class interval (IK) value could be explained in Table 1 above.

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Table 2. Construct Reliability Test

No.	Variabel	Cronbach alpha (CA)	Nilai Kritis	Keterangan
1.	Kemampuan Kerja	0,845	0,70	Reliabel
2.	<i>Servant Leadership</i>	0,847	0,70	Reliabel
3.	Beban Kerja	0,819	0,70	Reliabel
4.	Komitmen Organisasi	0,712	0,70	Reliabel
5.	Kinerja Karyawan	0,826	0,70	Reliabel

Source: SEM-PLS Output

The instrument reliability test is carried out after all indicators are able to pass the validity test. The reliability test is seen based on the Cronbach alpha (CA) value, the minimum condition of which is 0.70. For example, with the Cronbach alpha (CA) owned by each variable, it appears that Work Ability is supported by CA of 0.845 (CA > 0.70), Servant Leadership is supported by CA of 0.847 (CA > 0.70), Workload is supported by CA of 0.819 (CA > 0.70), Organizational Commitment supported by CA of 0.712 (CA > 0.70), and Employee Performance supported by CA of 0.826 (CA > 0.70). In other words, all latent variables used in this study have met the criteria for good instrument reliability.

B. Evaluation of Structural Model Fit

Figure 2. Structural Model Fit

In this study, the exogenous variables consist of the independent variables: Work Ability, Servant Leadership, and Workload, with an intervening variable: Organizational Commitment. These variables are analyzed for their influence on the dependent variable: Employee Performance.

Figure 2 above illustrates the structural equation model (Structural Equation Modeling or SEM) used to analyze the relationships between the variables in this study. The diagram shows how exogenous (independent) variables such as Work Ability (Kmpuan_K), Servant Leadership (Serv_Lead), and Workload (Beban_K) affect the endogenous (dependent) variable, Employee Performance (Kinj_Peg), with Organizational Commitment (Kom_Orgn) as the intervening variable.

Each latent variable (blue circles) is measured by several indicators (yellow boxes) connected by arrows. For example, Work Ability is measured by five indicators (X1_1 to X1_5), Servant Leadership by five indicators (X2_1 to X2_5), and Workload by three indicators (X3_1 to X3_3). Organizational Commitment is measured by three indicators (Z_1 to Z_3), and Employee Performance is measured by five indicators (Y_1 to Y_5).

The arrows indicate the direction of influence between variables, including direct paths from exogenous variables to endogenous variables and mediated paths through the intervening variable.

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C. Direct and Indirect Effect Analysis

Table 3. Direct Effect Analysis

Jalur pengaruh	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics	P Values	Keterangan
Kmpuan_K → Kinj_Peg	0,287	3,272	0,001	Signifikan
Kmpuan_K → Kom_Orgn	0,294	2,927	0,004	Signifikan
Serv_Lead → Kinj_Peg	0,217	2,229	0,026	Signifikan
Serv_Lead → Kom_Orgn	0,423	4,897	0,000	Signifikan
Beban_K → Kinj_Peg	-0,263	3,158	0,002	Signifikan
Beban_K → Kom_Orgn	-0,166	1,715	0,087	Tidak Signifikan
Kom_Orgn → Kinj_Peg	0,301	2,829	0,005	Signifikan

Source: SEM-PLS Output

Based on the results of the data analysis calculations displayed in the images and tables shown above, the research findings can be described and explained as follows:

1. Work Ability has an effect of 0.287 on Employee Performance. This influence is positive and accompanied by a t-statistic of 3.272 ($t \geq 1.96$) with a p-value of 0.001 ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the first hypothesis of this study is confirmed. The first hypothesis of this study, which states that "Work Ability influences the performance of employees at the East Java Province Department of Marine Affairs and Fisheries," is validated through the data analysis results. These findings align with previous studies by Elisa et al. (2022), Mujanah (2021), Mujanah & Arivani (2022), and Mailisa et al. (2016).
2. Work Ability has an effect of 0.294 on Organizational Commitment. This effect is positive and accompanied by a t-statistic of 3.148 ($t \geq 1.96$) with pvalue support of 0.004 ($p < 0.05$) which means that the 4th hypothesis in this study is confirmed. In other words, an increase in the value of Work Ability significantly has a positive effect on increasing Organizational Commitment. The second hypothesis of this study, which states that "Work ability has an effect on Organizational Commitment of Employees of the East Java Provincial Marine and Fisheries Service" was confirmed through the results of data analysis. These results confirm the results of previous studies by Herwati et al. (2022), Mailisa et al. (2016), and Prayogi et al. (2023). The findings of this study can describe a situation where an increase in Work Ability causes the value of Organizational Commitment in employees to increase significantly.
3. Servant Leadership has an effect of 0.217 on Employee Performance. This influence is positive and accompanied by a t-statistic of 3.272 ($t \geq 1.96$) with a p-value of 0.026 ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the second hypothesis of this study is confirmed. The third hypothesis of this study, which states that "Servant Leadership influences the performance of employees at the East Java Province Department of Marine Affairs and Fisheries," is validated through the data analysis results. These findings align with previous studies by Ludwikowska (2023), Pakpahan et al. (2021), Harwiki (2013), Fariana et al. (2022), Rachman et al. (2021), and Dani & Mujanah (2021).
4. Servant Leadership has an effect of 0.423 on Organizational Commitment. This influence is positive and accompanied by a t-statistic of 4.897 ($t \geq 1.96$) with a p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the fifth hypothesis of this study is confirmed. The fourth hypothesis of this study, which states that "Servant Leadership influences Organizational Commitment among employees of the East Java Province Department of Marine Affairs and Fisheries," is validated through the data analysis results. These findings align with previous studies by Tanuwijaya et al. (2023), Harwiki (2013), and Dani & Mujanah (2021). This study's findings also illustrate a situation where an increase in Servant Leadership leads to a significant improvement in Organizational Commitment among employees.
5. Workload has an effect of -0.263 on Employee Performance. This influence is negative and accompanied by a t-statistic of 3.158 ($t \geq 1.96$) with a p-value of 0.002 ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the third hypothesis of this study is confirmed. The fifth hypothesis of this study, which states that "Workload influences Employee Performance among employees of the East Java Province Department of Marine Affairs and Fisheries," is validated through the data analysis results. These findings align with previous studies by Juru & Wellem (2022), Fransiska & Tupti (2020), Nafiudin et al. (2023), and Saputra et al. (2023). This study also illustrates a situation where an increase in Workload leads to a decline in Employee Performance among employees.
6. Workload has an impact of -0.166 on Organizational Commitment. This impact is negative and accompanied by a t-statistic of 1.715 ($t \leq 1.96$) with a p-value of 0.087 ($p > 0.05$), indicating that the 6th hypothesis of this study is not confirmed. The sixth hypothesis of this study, which states that "Workload influences Organizational Commitment among employees of the East Java Province Department of Marine Affairs and Fisheries," cannot be validated through the data analysis results. These findings align with previous studies by Nafiudin et al. (2023) and Rafsanjani & Mujanah (2023). This study also illustrates a situation where an increase in Workload does not have a major influence on changes in employees' Organizational Commitment.

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7. Organizational Commitment has an impact of 0.301 on Employee Performance. This effect is positive and accompanied by a *t*-statistic of 2.829 ($t \geq 1.96$) with *p*-value support of 0.005 ($p < 0.05$) implies that the 7th hypothesis in this study is confirmed. The 7th hypothesis of this study which states "Organizational Commitment has an effect on the performance of employees of the East Java Provincial Marine and Fisheries Service" was confirmed through the results of data analysis. These results confirm the results of previous studies by Silaban et al. (2021), Elisa et al. (2022), Purwanto et al. (2022), Nafiudin et al. (2023), Marsilia et al. (2024), and Lestariningsih & Rismawati (2024). The findings of this study also illustrate the importance of Organizational Commitment to encourage Employee Performance and a situation where an increase in Work Ability causes the Employee Performance value to increase significantly. An expression of where an employee relates with the company and is linked to its objectives is organizational commitment (Kreitner & Kinicki, 2011). Organizational commitment is the condition in which a worker sides with an organization and its objectives and plans to keep its membership (Robbins, 2008). Robbins (2008) divides commitment into three forms, namely: affective, ongoing, and normative. Workers that show great emotional commitment feel emotionally connected to the organization, have a strong sense of pride and self-identity related to the organization where they work so that employees who have affective commitment will try to do their best work for the progress of the company. Higher the affective commitment, the more significant the influence on Employee Performance. Employees with ongoing commitment show that their attachment to the East Java Provincial Marine and Fisheries Service is because they are looking for good career opportunities. Employees with good normative commitment have a greater sense of moral responsibility to remain in the organization. Automatically, those with high degrees of normative dedication feel that they must remain loyal to the organization because of the values or social norms embedded in their perceptions, so that this type of employee will be more loyal and prioritize the best results to be given to the organization. From these explanations, it appears that Organizational Commitment has a significant influence on improving Employee Performance.

Table 4. Indirect Effect Analysis

Pengaruh Tidak Langsung	Besarnya pengaruh	<i>T statistics</i>	<i>P Values</i>	Ket.
Kmpuan_K → Kom_Orgn → Kinj_Peg	0,088	1,919	0,056	Tidak Memediasi
Serv_Lead → Kom_Orgn → Kinj_Peg	0,127	2,236	0,026	Memediasi
Beban_K → Kom_Orgn → Kinj_Peg	-0,050	1,279	0,202	Tidak memediasi

Source: SEM-PLS Output

In structural equation modeling in data analysis with smart-PLS, indirect effects do not need to be calculated manually because the results of the indirect effect calculations are listed in the output of the inner model evaluation results with the term specific indirect effects. Details of the findings of the specific indirect effect calculation results are shown in table 4 above.

The calculation results in the table above show results that can be explained one by one as follows:

1. The Work Ability variable has an effect of 0.088 on Employee Performance through the Organizational Commitment variable. This effect is positive and supported by *t* statistics of 1.919 ($t < 1.96$) and *p* values of 0.056 (p values > 0.05) which means that the mediation role of this Work Ability variable is not significant or in other words that Organizational Commitment cannot mediate the effect of Work Ability on Employee Performance.
2. The Servant Leadership variable has an impact of 0.127 on Employee Performance through the Organizational Commitment variable. This effect is positive and supported by *t* statistics of 2.236 ($t > 1.96$) and *p* values of 0.026 (p values < 0.05) which means that the mediation role of the Workload variable is significant or in other words that Organizational Commitment mediates the effect of Servant Leadership on Employee Performance.
3. The Workload variable has an effect of 0.084 on Employee Performance through the Organizational Commitment variable. This effect is negative and supported by *t* statistics of 1.279 ($t < 1.96$) and *p* values of 0.202 (p values > 0.05) which means that the mediating role of the Organizational Commitment variable is not significant or in other words that Organizational Commitment does not mediate the effect of Workload on Employee Performance.

VI. CONCLUSION

1. The first hypothesis was confirmed to be true, this implies that should work ability rise, then, the Performance of Employees will also increase significantly.
2. The second hypothesis was confirmed to be true, this implies that should work ability rise, then, the Organizational Commitment of the East Java Provincial Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Service will also increase significantly.
3. The third hypothesis was confirmed to be true, which means that if there is an increase in Servant Leadership, the Performance of Employees of the East Java Provincial Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Service will also increase significantly.
4. The 4th hypothesis was confirmed to be true, which means that if there is an increase in Servant Leadership, the Organizational Commitment of the East Java Provincial Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Service will also increase significantly.

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5. The 5th hypothesis was confirmed to be true, which means that if there is an increase in the workload, the performance of employees of the East Java Provincial Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Service will decrease significantly.
6. The 6th hypothesis was not confirmed to be true, which means that if there is an increase in the Workload, the Organizational Commitment of the East Java Provincial Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Service will not decrease.
7. The 7th hypothesis was confirmed to be true, which means that if there is an increase in Organizational Commitment, the Performance of Employees of the East Java Provincial Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Service will also increase significantly.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research findings and given the findings that have been discussed in the preceding paragraphs, these are some of the ideas that might be put forward:

1. Suggestions for the East Java Provincial Marine and Fisheries Service

It is clear from the findings of the research that workload is unable to have a significant impact on the decline in Organizational Commitment. This is something that deserves attention because it is a good thing where workload does not always have a negative impact on Organizational Commitment in the employees of the East Java Provincial Marine and Fisheries Service Secretariat. In addition, it is hoped that through these findings, the leadership and management will pay attention to the workload that has been felt by employees so that the impact in the future will not be negative on Employee Performance.

2. Suggestions for further researchers

Future research may incorporate additional variables beyond those independent variables examined in this study because the variables in question are only able to explain Organizational Commitment by 37.4% and Employee Performance by 52.7%, which means that Organizational Commitment and Employee Performance can still be explained by other variables so that it is still possible to be added to further research

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